

Technological Development of Polymer based Composites containing Nano Materials for Brake pad Applications

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Abstract—Brake pads are a crucial component of an automobile's braking system, and the materials used in them must be highly resistant to wear, stable, and reliable under a variety of loads, velocities, temperatures, and environmental conditions. Using either manual, hydraulic, or pneumatic techniques, friction materials in the shape of brake pad is applied to the disc's both sides in order to slow down an automobile. In this case, an organic frictional material was created through powder metallurgy, which included solid lubricant, coconut fiber, friction modifiers, and abrasive elements. Since asbestos fiber is known to have carcinogenic properties and pose health risks, a new brake pad made of non-asphalt materials instead of asbestos fibers is created in this study.

Keywords: Brake pads, Nano-materials, Asbestos free, Organic materials, Automobile

INTRODUCTION

Component that is used in automobiles and in various applications to lessen friction is the brake pad. They are made up of steel backing plates with friction material affixed to the disc brake rotor-facing side. Two brake pads are housed in each calliper, their friction surfaces facing the rotor. Brake pads were first composed of carbon and asbestos, bound together by an extremely durable resin. In disc brake systems, the two brake pads on each disc rotor are usually held in place and controlled by callipers attached to the wheel hub or suspension upright. The brake pads' longevity is directly impacted by the braking technique. The design of brake pads prioritizes the reduction of noise and vibration, stability of friction, and durability. Whether in lubricated or dry situations, the ideal brake friction material should retain a constant frictional coefficient for a range of operational parameters, such as applied loads, temperatures, speeds, and braking types.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY:

Darius G. Solomon and Mohamad. (2007)[1] The comparison of New friction material formulations are done for commercial braking material utilised in Malaysia's Light Rail Transit (LRT). For characterisation, they employ friction and wear tests, TGA, XRD, and SEM. S1 and S2, two of the thirty formulations, closely resemble the brand-name product. The wear resistance and thermal stability of Formulation S2 are excellent. S2 possesses the same crystallinity as the commercial specimen, according to SEM analysis, physical characteristics, and XRD spectrum analysis, indicating that it could take the place of the commercial material in LRT brake pads. The cost might be cut in

half if these brake pads were produced locally in Malaysia.

Aleksander Yevtushenko · Michal Kuciej · Olena Yevtushenko. (2010)[12], This work investigates the quasi-static thermal stresses and the accompanying transient temperature field in a system consisting of a strip and a semi-space. A heat flow equivalent to the frictional power during braking with uniform retardation heats the outside surface of the strip. For the metal-ceramic FMK-11 material, the study investigates temperature and thermal stress scattering far from the friction surface. Another variation involves conceptually separating the friction pair elements and allocating heat fluxes to each friction surface in such a way that the total of them equals the frictional power. The heat participation factor is presented by empirical formulas or experimental methods. There are solutions offered for homogenous or composite strips that have heat conduction issues during braking. The study also looks into the thermal strains brought on by heating with a consistent heat pulse.

Z.U. Elakhame, O.A. Alhassan, A.E. Samuel. (2014)[2], The goal in the project is to replace asbestos, which is carcinogenic, with palm kernel shell (PKS) to create brake pads free of asbestos. PKS was graded into 100, 350, 710 μm , and 1 mm sieves before being compressed into a combination of 55% PKS and 0–20% SiC. Among the attributes examined are microstructure, flame resistance, compressive strength, hardness, density, and water and oil absorption. According to the microstructure analysis, PKS exhibits a uniform resin dispersion. Finer filter diameters provide better quality results. When the results were compared to top laboratory formulations and commercial asbestos-based brake pads, they showed good agreement. This suggests that PKS may be utilised to make brake pads without asbestos quite well. The final composition of the brake pad formulation was 15% steel, 10% graphite, and 20% resin.

Loganathan, Yuvaraj & S, Jeyanthi. (2015)[3], Due to the carcinogenic effects of asbestos fibers, kenaf and banana peel powder were utilised in the development of a new brake pad. The binder used is Phenolic resin, and its chemical impact was investigated at intervals of 5 weight percent to 30 weight percent. The study focused on the mechanical characteristics of natural fiber-based brake pads, including their density, porosity, and compressive stress. The findings showed that as resin concentration grew, so did specific gravity, hardness, and compressive strength. The batch with 10% kenaf powder and 25% banana peel powder showed superior mechanical qualities.

C Pinca-Bretotean1, A Josan1 and C Birtok-Băneasă1. (2017)[5], Brake pads are essential in vehicle braking systems, requiring

materials with exceptional durability and consistent frictional and wear properties under various conditions. This study explores an organic frictional material created using powder metallurgy with coconut fiber, abrasives, friction modifiers, and solid lubricants. The material underwent laboratory testing, with results presented here. The analysis, conducted on a specially designed installation, examined the temperature field, density, porosity, hardness, mechanical characteristics, friction coefficient evolution, and the region where the brake pad and disc come into touch. The laboratory results offer a comprehensive understanding of the material's performance.

Brake pads have to be strong and maintain consistent, dependable frictional and wear characteristics throughout a range of loads, speeds, temperatures, and environmental conditions, according to C. Pinca-Bretotean, A. Josan, and C. Birtok-Băneasă. Using powder metallurgy, they developed an organic frictional material comprising solid lubricants, abrasives, coconut fiber, and friction modulator. This research describes laboratory tests of this material making use of a customised installation, with an emphasis on density, porosity, hardness, mechanical properties, evolution of the friction coefficient, and temperature fields in the contact region between the disc and brake pad. The outcomes paint a clear picture of the performance of the produced material.

Abutu S. A. Lawal, M. B. Ndaliman, R. A. Lafa-Arag Adedip-I. A. Choudhury. (2018)[4], This study used locally sourced, non-hazardous materials to produce brake pads via grey relational analysis (GRA) and central composite design. The raw materials included coconut shell (reinforcement), epoxy resin (binder), graphite (friction modifier), and aluminum oxide (abrasive). Twenty-seven samples were produced by varying process parameters, with a formulation of 52% reinforcement, 35% binder, 8% abrasive, and 5% friction modifier. GRA determined the optimal process parameters as 14 MPa molding pressure, 140 °C molding temperature, 8-minute curing time, and 5-hour heat treatment time. The optimized sample, produced using these parameters, was compared to a commercially available sample from Ibeto Group. Results showed the optimized coconut shell-reinforced brake pad performed comparably to commercial samples, producing less brake noise and vibration. Analysis of variance indicated curing time significantly affected hardness (30.38%) and tensile strength (31.40%), while heat treatment time significantly affected wear rate (46.3%) and friction coefficient (24.23%). All factors were significant, with p-values greater than 0.01.

Miss. Tengale Gauri, Prof. A. K. Biradar. (2018)[6], -Vehicles like trucks, buses, cars, and bikes frequently use disc brakes. Although disc brake materials have received a lot of attention, the friction material in the brake calliper is just as significant since it plays a part in stopping. Research on braking materials has mostly focused on temperature analysis and coefficient of friction; abrasion behaviour has received less attention. Using a spinning wheel-type device and angular silica abrasives, this study examines the abrasion behaviour of braking materials under various test settings.

Adekunle N. O., Oladejo K. A., Kuye S. I. and Aikulola A. D. (2019)[11], Since asbestos is potentially dangerous, brake pads made of asbestos are not desired. This study assessed brake pads composed of bamboo leaves that were free of asbestos. We sieved ground bamboo leaves into three grades: 100, 200, and 350 µm. To develop different formulations of brake pads, these particles were blended with 15% steel dust, 20% resin, 10% graphite, and silicon carbide, varying from 35 to 55%. Investigations were conducted into the mechanical characteristics, such as compressive strength hardness, density, porosity, flame resistance and wear rate. The findings showed that improved mechanical qualities were produced by finer bamboo leaf particles.

İlker Sugözü and Banu Sugözü (2021)[9], Brake linings are made by carefully choosing and mixing materials with different qualities; the sizes and ratios have a big impact on consistency and performance. These linings are intricate composites made of fillers, binders, solid lubricants, abrasives, friction modifiers, and reinforcing fibres. Achieving a high friction coefficient and superior wear resistance is the main goal when choosing a friction material. Furthermore, these materials need to be able to keep their friction coefficient constant in harsh environments like hot temperatures. For friction pairs to develop effectively, it is also important to ensure compatibility with the counterpart material, prevent damage, and maintain a stable, high friction coefficient in challenging circumstances.

Melkamu Yigrem, O. Fatoba Sheferaw Tensay. (2022)[8], A composite formulation incorporating carbon powder and banana peel, along with bronze and hardener, exhibits exceptional friction resistance properties, capable of withstanding high temperatures and pressures in operational settings. Composition 1 demonstrated an increase in both elongation and stress, achieving a utmost stress output of 2.1 MPa and elongation of approximately 13.0. In the Composition 2, featuring a higher percentage of banana peel waste (35 wt%), achieved an output stress of 1.8 MPa, while reducing the weight percentage of carbon powder resulted in a 14.3% decrease in stress output but a 20.5% increase in elongation. Finally in Composition 3, with powdered banana peel was

increased to 40%, stress output further decreased to around 1.40 MPa. Composition 1 also exhibited minimal weight loss and maintained the maximum strength of 2.1 MPa and elongation of 13.0. Correlation between weight and strength variations was observed, highlighting Composition 1 as particularly suitable for brake pad applications due to its minimal banana peel content and high carbon powder content.

3. OBJECTIVES:

The goal is development of brake pad material for automotive application. The Taguchi method is adopted as a part of design of experiment. To functionalize hybrid polymer composite brake pad in order to increase its efficiency.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY:

4.1 MATERIAL

The primary objective is to develop non-asbestos brake pad composites by substituting conventional fillers, such as asbestos or other organic and inorganic materials, with palm slag. The study examined various processing pressures and palm slag size distributions used in the production of brake pads. Dolomite and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) were used as alternative fillers in comparative investigations.

4.2 RAW MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

Characterizing the raw materials was crucial to understanding the specifics of each material used in the research. Thorough characterization it is aimed to identify potential risks that could impact product performance and to Establish measures to reduce these potential risk when creating multi-component composites, such as brake pad materials, it is crucial to comprehend the characteristics of each source element. Establishing a thorough knowledge based on the raw materials used in formulations and the effects they have on product performance is the goal of detailed raw material characterization. The interactions of these components within a tribological system, however, may not be accurately represented by chemical and physical characterizations, which usually describe the raw material itself. Various types of characterization methods were employed to achieve this understanding, including chemical, physical, and other relevant techniques. Different types of characterization is discussed below.

CHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION

An XRF spectrometer is an X-ray instrument used for routine, mostly non-destructive chemical analyses of rocks, sediments, minerals and fluids. Operating concepts are based on dispersive wavelength

spectroscopic principles and are similar to those of an electron probe micro analyzer (EPMA). A Mini PAL 4 standard less mode ED-XRF spectrometer was used to analyze the chemical makeup of the palm slag. The standard characterization needed for the manufacture of brake pads depends on this analysis.

THERMAL CHARACTERIZATION

A thermal analysis method called thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) is used to determine how a sample's weight changes with temperature. The process of analysis can be carried out in reactive atmospheres or under nitrogen and air. A pair of photodiodes are used to detect the displacement of the balance beam, working on the null-balance principle. The sample is heated in a low thermal resistance furnace, and its temperature—which is measured along the X-axis—is tracked by a thermocouple next to the sample pan. The thermogram, also known as the thermal decomposition curve, is the resultant plot of mass or mass percent vs time or temperature.

Using the same experimental setup, TGA was carried out on distinct combinations of dolomite, palm slag, or calcium carbonate as filler and phenolic resin as the binder to simulate a brake pad. Ten milligramme sample weights were tracked over a 30-to 1000°C temperature range using nitrogen as the inert gas. Taking into account temperature conditions, wear, and other attributes, this characterization is essential for the design, fabrication, and manufacturing processes.

Alumina: Alternatively known as commercially manufactured aluminium oxide, Al_2O_3 , or aluminium oxide, this white or almost colourless crystalline material serves as a precursor for smelting aluminium metal.

Thermoplastic Polyimide Resin: A part of thermoplastic polymer family (Nylon, Kevlar), polyamide (PA) resins can be produced with heat and remelted without losing their inherent properties.

Glass Powder: It is a substance made up of several incredibly fine glass fibers.

Banana Peel Powder: Banana peel is a well-known source of potassium and is high in natural fibre. By adding banana peel powder as an additive, the flexural strength of the concrete has increased, but the compressive strength has increased much less.

Graphite Powder: Chemical stability, high cycle life counts, enhanced adhesion, and greater capacity are all provided by the graphite powder.

Molybdenum disulfide: It is an inorganic compound made up of sulphur and molybdenum. MoS_2 is its chemical formula.

Graphene: Graphene is a carbon allotrope made up of a single layer of atoms arranged in a two-dimensional honeycomb lattice nanostructure. The suffix-ene and the word "graphite" are the sources of the name, which indicates the abundance of double bonds found in the graphite

allotrope of carbon.

Cast Iron Powder: To provide the necessary friction, iron powder is frequently used in drum brake linings, brake pads, and other applications. Iron powder serves as a filler that improves the functionality and longevity of these items by efficiently dispersing heat produced during operation.

Zeolite Powder: Zeolites are three-dimensional, crystalline solids of aluminium silicate that are microporous. Zeolites are sometimes referred to as molecular sieves because of the tiny, fixed-size pores in them that permit small molecules to flow past them readily but prevent larger ones from doing so.

Silicon Carbide : Silicon carbide, additionally referred to as carborundum, is a solid chemical compound composed of silicon and carbon. This semiconductor is found in nature as the extremely uncommon mineral moissanite, but since 1893, it has been mass-produced for abrasive applications as a powder and crystal.

Carboxymethyl Cellulose : Some of the hydroxyl groups of the glucopyranose monomers that make up the cellulose backbone are linked by carboxymethyl groups in order to form carboxymethyl cellulose, also referred to as cellulose gum. It is commonly used as its sodium salt, sodium carboxymethyl cellulose.

Clay Minerals : Minerals made of clay are great as absorbers, adsorbents, and clarifiers. Because of their affordability, availability, and versatility, they are widely used in a variety of industrial applications, such as those in the food and pharmaceutical industries, as well as the paper, ceramic, cement, petroleum adhesive, paint and asphalt industries.

Table 1.1: Property of Composites for Brake pad

SI no	Elements	Density/ g/cm ³	Weight %	Grams to be used for Single Brake pad	Grams to be used for 5 pairs
1	Aluminum Oxide	3.95	8.294	1.036	5.18
2	Thermoplastic Polyimide Resin	1.13-1.15	2.393	0.3	1.5
3	Coconut Fibers	0.67-10.0	11.203	1.4	7
4	Coconut Fiber	1.6	3.359	0.5	2.5
5	Glass Fiber	2.44-2.52	5.207	0.7	3.5
6	Banana Peel Powder	1.3815-1.4991	3.024	0.4	2
7	Graphite Powder	1.8	3.779	0.5	2.5
8	Fly Ash	1.9-2.9	5.039	0.628	3.14
9	Cellulose Powder	1.5	3.149	0.4	2
10	Graphene	2.267	4.76	0.6	3
11	Molybdenum Di Sulfide	5.06	10.625	1.4	7
12	Graphite	2.26	4.745	0.6	3
13	Cast Iron	7.2	15.119	2	10
14	Steel Wool	7.16	15.032	1.9	9.5

	Powders				
15	Zeolites Dust	0.6-0.86	1.532	0.2	1
16	Phenolic Resin	1.2-1.4	2.729	0.341	1.705
	Total		99.989	12.905	

Table 1.2: Above Material Classified into Positively and Negative Charged Materials

Weight (Grams)	Graded Inputs	Different Materials	Positively Charged	Negatively Charged	Half Cell Potential
20	Binders	Thermoplastic Polyimide Resin		(-)	
5	Reinforce Cement	Alumina	Neutral		-1.662
2		Coconut Fiber		(-)	-1.12
5		Coconut Shell Powder	Low PH (+)	High PH (-)	1
5.5	Reinforce Cement	Glass Fiber	(+)		-0.86
6		Banana Peel Powder	(+)		-1.2
5	Fillers	Graphite powder	(+)		0.34
28		Fly Ash	Surface Charge	Surface Charge	0.34
4		Cellulose Powder		(-)	0.12
1	Abrasives	Graphene	Neutral		0.34
0.5		Molybdenum Di Sulfide		(-)	1.23
2		Graphite	(+)		0.34
3		Cast Iron Powder	Neutral		1.23
3		Steel Wool Powders	15.032	(-)	
10		Zeolites Dust	1.532	(-)	0.1
100		Phenolic Resin	(+)	(-)	

5. PREPARATION OF COMPOSITE SAMPLES MIXING

To achieve a homogenous state, raw ingredients were blended in the first step of sample preparation. The initially created substance consisted of a mixture of different-sized and compositional powders plus a binder. To cut down on explosion risks and dust emissions, the mixing was done in a dry environment. To ensure consistency in the chemical composition and the distribution of component sizes and shapes, large batches of powder were homogenized.

The raw components were then mixed in a ball mill machine and put in a closed bottle that was sandwiched between two rollers. The formula $N = 32/\sqrt{d}$, where d is the drum diameter in meters and N is the speed in RPM, was used to calculate the rotational milling speed for the cylindrical mixer. Smaller diameters necessitate faster speeds for equivalent optimization; a cylinder with a diameter of one meter, for instance, has an ideal speed of 32 RPM. The degree of raw material in homogeneity affects the mixing rate.

The raw materials in the nip experience severe shear as the rolls rotate in opposing directions. A 100-gram mix on a two-roll ball mill requires roughly three hours of mixing time, depending on the operator. The following filler components were combined: steel fibers, phenolic resin, alumina powder, graphite powder, and palm slag, CaCO₃, or dolomite. To guarantee homogeneity, the mixtures were processed in a two-roll ball mill for three hours at 273 RPM with 50 balls in the mill jar. The formula for a 13 cm diameter jar mill was used to determine the speed of 273 RPM.

Fig 1.1: Mixing of Resin and Binder with weight Measurement

Fig 1.2: Mixed Materials Measured before Mixing of Resin & Binder Mixing of Resin & Binder

Fig 1.3: Mixing of Resin & Binder Materials Measured after

6.COMPACTION

When cold compressing powder materials at ambient temperature, a process known as "cold compaction," high-temperature deformation mechanisms including dislocation and diffusion creep can be skipped. This method uses robust steel dies with axially loaded punches to compact powder. The homogeneous materials are compressed using cold compaction machinery after milling. At room temperature, the loose powder condenses into a structure called a green body or compact. In the compacted materials, high density and homogeneous density distribution are usually desirable properties. Powder metallurgy is the process by which the powder particles mostly travel in the direction of the applied force during compaction.

The components of the brake pad are prepared for moulding and compaction after being ground into a uniform mixture. In order to keep the powder from sticking to the mold's surface, lubricate it with WD-40 before adding the mixture to it. After that, the milling mixture is poured into the mould and compressed using a uni-axial, hydraulic hand press machine at a pressure of 15–17 MPa. Green bodies of the brake pad composite materials are created by shaping the components of the brake pad into a mould while it is at room temperature. After that, these green bodies undergo more curing and compacting. The mould design dictates the size and form of these samples; each specimen is compressed into a cylindrical shape with

a diameter of 10.

Fig 1.4: Hydraulic Compressor for the Cold Press for Brake Pad

Fig 1.5: Mold used for Cold Press with Brake Pad Material Fill

7. METHODOLOGY FOR THE PROCESS FLOW OF PROJECT

The overall methodology is depicted in the flow chart below.

8. RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

To meet the objectives, the findings and discussions for these investigations were arranged into four primary areas. The characterization of the raw materials—which includes thermal behavior study using TGA and chemical composition analysis using XRF for all relevant materials—were discussed in the first section. The effects of various filler materials on the compressive strength, wear characteristics, density, and hardness of the brake pads was explored. The study suggests that palm slag can be used in brake pad composites in place of other fillers, based on the mechanical and wear qualities. Organic compounds have a great deal of potential as a substitute material for use in brake pad composites, as shown by comparisons with other fillers. Even when compared to asbestos, the densities of the nanomaterial composites showed their viability for use as brake pads because they are lightweight.

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